

Optimal Short-Term Dispatch of Insular Systems: the Case of Ikaria

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Abstract—The energy transition in islands poses a significant challenge, yet it also presents a considerable opportunity for sustainable social and economic development. A promising evolution towards this direction emerged recently in Greek islands. Although there are several research studies exploring the effect of the integration of Energy Storage Systems (ESS) in the long-term planning of Greek insular systems, little attention has been paid towards the short-term Dispatch. In this paper, a day-ahead optimal dispatch strategy is presented for the Ikaria island, a pioneer in the pathway towards decarbonization and clean energy transition of Greece. Ikaria possesses a Hybrid Power Plant (HPP) consisting of three Wind Turbines (WTs) and a hydro-pump storage (HPS). However, still the exploitation of the HPP is limited due to its current operating mode. The aim of this study is to construct an optimization framework considering operational aspects and CO₂ emissions with particular emphasis on the HPS and thermal unit modelling so as to lift the barriers for the operators and help increase the Renewable Energy Sources (RES) penetration, minimize CO₂ emissions in Ikaria, optimize islands interconnection management and transform Ikaria into a paradigm insular system with respect to its short-term dispatch and control operation.

Index Terms—hybrid power plants, hydro-pump storage, insular systems, renewable energy sources

I. INTRODUCTION

The transition to sustainable energy in islands presents both a notable challenge and a substantial opportunity for fostering sustainable social and economic development while enhancing security of supply. Nowadays, this transition focuses on utilizing Renewable Energy Sources (RES), combined with energy storage systems (ESS), thus, creating “hybrid power plants” (HPPs), [1]–[3]. For larger islands with demand larger than 5 MW, hydro-pumped storage systems (HPSS) [4], [5] have proven to be the optimal ESS technology, able to provide high ESS capacity, extended autonomy, and relatively low setup cost (EUR 30/kWh) [6]. In addition, HPSS can contribute to

frequency regulation through the rapid and flexible operation of hydro turbines and pump load management [7], as well as voltage control, [1]. Two successfully operating wind power parks (WPPs) integrated with HPSS are found on the El Hierro islands in the Canary Islands, Spain [8], and Ikaria island in the Eastern Aegean Sea, Greece [9].

Generally, the incorporation of HPSS in larger scale Power Systems has been explored in [4], [5], [10], [11]. Specifically, the study [10] presents an optimal hourly management model of grid-connected Photovoltaic Power Plants (PVPPs) and WPPs integrated with reversible pump-turbine units to maximize the monthly operating profits and meet electricity demand in the Spanish System. The studies [4], [5] explore the integration of HPSS in the Argentinian Power System and develop mathematical models to minimize the electricity cost or maximize the revenue profit of the HPSS. In [11] the authors model the operation of a HPSS and suggest possible operating policies under schemes of peak load supply and wind generation firming.

Focusing on Greek insular systems, in [9] the operation of the Ikaria islanded distribution network (IDN) and the existing HPSS are simulated on an annual hourly basis taking into account the existing regulatory framework so as to quantify the long-term benefits from the HPSS operation in a day-ahead (DA) dispatch model based on power balance. In [12] the potential use of the Potamon Dam in Crete is explored as a HPSS with the goal to harness and maximize the utilization of excess wind energy that the IDN of Crete cannot accommodate. In [8] the effect of installing a HPP consisting of a WPP/HPSS on the operation of the Samos IDN is studied, considering several HPSS sizes and the associated economic viability based on annual hourly data under various billing schemes.

The above studies focus mainly on the long-term planning of IDNs with HPSS/HPPs and the optimal HPSS size to ensure economic viability. The Ikaria IDN is a particular IDN in terms of geographical and operational landscape, since it contains

three water reservoirs interconnected in tandem. Currently, this IDN runs its daily operation on rule-based solutions where the HPSS is not utilized in an optimal manner. Building upon the Development Plans (DPs) of the Greek Distribution Network Operator (DNO) and Transmission System Operator (TSO) described in the following sections, in this paper, specific contributions regard the DA optimal dispatch exploiting all assets of the Ikaria IDN, i.e., WPPs, PVs and pumps. Note that the Greek geographical landscape could favor solutions with HPSS in expansion studies. In the DA the optimization is performed considering the minimization of CO2 emissions and RES curtailments, contrary to previous studies, [4], [5]. In addition, this study contains the expansion of Ikaria IDN after 2010, [9], and future operation Scenarios. This work is developed within the Horizon Europe project SINNOGENES, which aims at developing a Digital Twin (DT) for Ikaria IDN that will integrate several components to facilitate the DA and near real-time Intra-Day (ID) operation. The components will include: forecasting tools for weather prediction, RES generation and load consumption, a DA active power dispatch tool, a power flow tool and an ID active/reactive power dispatch tool. The DT will consider the operation of the non-interconnected IDN and its future operation as an interconnected DN with the mainland to see if Ikaria could provide more renewable energy and several ancillary services (AS) to other IDNs and the mainland Transmission System (TS). For this reason, the proposed optimization set-up will serve as a basis for conducting feasibility studies for the optimal use and AS provision capability with respect to the interconnection with the Samos IDN and with the Greek mainland TS, as envisioned in the DPs of the Greek DNO and TSO.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section II presents the detailed topology of the Ikaria Greek IDN and the DPs of the Greek DNO and TSO. Section III provides the optimization framework for the DA operation. Section IV analyzes the results of the proposed optimization on the Ikaria IDN. Finally, Section V closes this paper with its main findings, and suggests future directions.

II. INSULAR SYSTEM UNDER STUDY

A. Current Operation of the Ikaria IDN

The Ikaria IDN load varies from 2-8 MW. The respective generation assets depicted in Fig. 1 consist of: (a) a conventional Autonomous Local Fuel Power Station (ALFPS), which comprises of 11 heavy fuel oil (mazut/diesel) units - 4 of which are portable- with a total capacity of 15.6 MW, [9]; (b) two WPPs of 0.6 MW and 0.3MW that are considered as one WPP of 0.9MW in the current DA scheduling; (c) the HPSS; (d) three PVPPs: one PVPP of 100kW_p and two PVPPs of 150kW_p each. The PVPPs currently are not considered in the DA scheduling but will be included in this study. The Ikaria HPSS comprises of three water reservoirs at different altitudes above sea level, a pump station, two small hydroelectric plants (SHPs) and a 2.7 MW_p WPP. Specifically, the 2.7 MW_p WPP, located at Stravokountoura, consists of 3×0.9 MW_p variable speed Enercon E44 Wind Turbines (WTs), [9]. The pumping

Fig. 1. Single Line Diagram of the Ikaria IDN

station is located at Kato Proespera, comprising 8×250 kW fixed speed (FSPs) and 4×250 kW variable speed pumps (VSPs). The VSPs have a setting range from 160-250 kW, and have priority for inclusion, while the FSPs are controlled by a soft starter of installed power 250 kW/unit. The minimum loading of the pumps is 50%, i.e., 125kW. Currently, in order to integrate a new pump, necessary conditions include: (a) the already installed VSPs operate at full power; (b) the theoretical production capacity of the WPP is greater than the current power of the Pump Station during the power step of integrating an additional pump (250kW). In this study, it was assumed that one additional pump can be integrated with its 50% loading.

With respect to the water storage, a reservoir at Pezi (900,000 m³) is currently used for irrigation and water supply and its excess water is exploited for energy generation purposes. Two other reservoirs at Proespera and Kato Proespera (80,000 m³ each) are utilized for HPSS. The two reservoirs are linked hydraulically via a dual penstock system ensuring that generation and pumping operations remain separate and independent from each other. Furthermore, one SHP with a 1.05 MW Pelton turbine is interconnected at Proespera, leveraging surplus water from the Pezi dam utilizing a pressure head of 167 m. Another SHP with two Pelton 1.55 MW turbines is connected to Kato Proespera exploiting a pressure head of $\Delta h_{P,KP}$ to participate in HPSS operation. The turbines of the SHPs are denoted as SHP turbines (SHPTs). The water capacity of the HPSS is calculated via potential energy difference between Proespera (P) and Kato Proespera (KP):

$$E_{P,KP}^{Cap} = V \cdot \rho \cdot g \cdot \Delta h_{P,KP} \quad (1)$$

where $V=80.000m^3$ is the volume of both vessels, $\rho=1,000kg/m^3$ is the density of water, $g=9.81m/s^2$ is gravity acceleration, Δh is the elevation difference of both vessels, specifically $h_P = 555.2m$ a.s.l. and $h_{KP} = 50.7m$ a.s.l., [3], [9], hence, $\Delta h_{P,KP} = h_P - h_{KP}=504.5m$.

TABLE I
PARAMETER DEFINITIONS AND VALUES

Parameter	Value/Range	Unit	Definition
$m_{\text{Diesel-ON}}$	5	[kg]	Diesel Mass consumed in cold start
$m_{\text{Mazut-ON}}$	150	[kg]	Mazut Mass consumed in cold start
$c_{\text{thermal}}^{\text{var}}$	403.42	[€/MWh]	Variable cost of thermal units
$c_{\text{thermal}}^{\text{ope}}$	316.15	[€/MWh]	Operation cost of thermal units
$c_{\text{fuel}}^{\text{mazut}}$	576.31	[€/t]	Fuel cost per tonne of mazut
$c_{\text{fuel}}^{\text{diesel}}$	1161.51	[€/t]	Fuel cost per tonne of diesel
C_{HPSS}	295	[€/MWh]	Generation cost of the HPSS
c_{Pump}	109	[€/MWh]	Cost of pumping (not considered in this study)
c_{PV}	353.38	[€/MWh]	Generation cost of the PVPP
c_{Wind}	100	[€/MWh]	Generation cost of the WPP
η_{P}	0.899	[p.u.]	Proespera SHPT Efficiency
$\eta_{\text{KP1,2}}$	0.899	[p.u.]	Kato Proespera SHPTs Efficiency
η_{Pumps}	0.7298	[p.u.]	Kato Proespera pumps Efficiency
$E_{\text{P,KP}}^{\text{Cap}}$	110	[MWh]	Water capacity of Proespera-KatoProespera storage system
$\text{CO}_2^{\text{diesel}}$	3.19	[tCO ₂ /tFuel]	CO ₂ emissions of diesel, [13]
$\text{CO}_2^{\text{mazut}}$	3.15	[tCO ₂ /tFuel]	CO ₂ emissions of mazut, [13]
$\text{CO}_2^{\text{HPSS}}$	0.011	[tCO ₂ /MWh]	CO ₂ emissions of the HPSS, [14]
$\text{CO}_2^{\text{Wind}}$	0.013	[tCO ₂ /MWh]	CO ₂ emissions of the WPP, [14]
CO_2^{PV}	0.026	[tCO ₂ /MWh]	CO ₂ emissions of the PVPP, [14]
c_{CO_2}	70	[€/tCO ₂]	Emissions cost, [15]
P_{SMR}	60	[% demand]	Minimum synchronous power connected to ensure grid stability and inertia factor, [7]
P_{P}^{t}	[0.105, 1.05]	[MW]	Power produced by Proespera SHPT
$P_{\text{KP1,2}}^{\text{t}}$	[0.155, 1.55]	[MW]	Power produced by Kato Proespera SHPTs 1 and 2
$P_{\text{pumps}}^{\text{t}}$	[0.125, 3]	[MW]	Power consumed by the pumping station with priority to VSPs
P_{LD}^{t}	[2, 8]	[MW]	Power consumed in Ikaria
$P_{\text{HPSS}}^{\text{t}}$	[-3, +4.15]	[MW]	HPSS power (from full pump to full turbine)

A distinguishing feature of the Ikaria HPSS, setting it apart from typical configurations, is its integration of two RES: wind power through pumped storage and hydroelectricity via utilizing surplus water from the upper reservoir, all within a single hydraulic infrastructure. Pumping saving is achieved through a separate pressure pipeline, elevating water from the lower to the intermediate reservoir, synchronizing the pumping station's consumption of 3MW total power with the 2.70 MW output of the WPP. During the winter months, the HPSS utilizes the SHPs to harness the Pezi dam and the two reservoirs for hydroelectric power generation, capitalizing on the natural overflow of the Pezi dam. When wind potential is present, synchronization occurs between the WPP and the Pumping Station to pump and store water as "hybrid" energy in the reservoirs. This process effectively converts stochastic wind energy into dynamic water energy, which is then utilized for supplying hydroelectric power to meet the IDN load. More details about the components can be found in [9], [16].

B. DPs of the Greek DNO and TSO

Based on the DP of Hellenic DNO (HEDNO), the Greek DNO, the interconnection of Ikaria and Samos IDNs is necessary for [17] the utilization of the exported energy from the Ikaria HPSS to Samos and the interconnection of the North-East Aegean islands. Initially, the interconnection will be achieved via a submarine MV interconnection with two cables $3 \times 95 \text{mm}^2$ Cu, 45.69 km long each. The new submarine cables will be connected to the existing MV overhead IDN of Samos. Later on, based on the Ten Year DP of the Independent Power Transmission Operator (IPTO), the Greek TSO, Samos will obtain power from the Greek HV TS through of a new

HV/MV substation in place of the current Samos ALFPS, [18]. However, no more details are provided in the TSO DP in force.

III. DAY AHEAD OPTIMIZATION FRAMEWORK

In this section, the DA optimization framework is presented. The parameters used in the framework and associated are values are shown in Table I. The values of $m_{\text{Diesel-ON}}$, $m_{\text{Mazut-ON}}$, $C_{\text{thermal}}^{\text{var}}$, $C_{\text{thermal}}^{\text{ope}}$, $C_{\text{fuel}}^{\text{diesel}}$, $C_{\text{fuel}}^{\text{mazut}}$, C_{HPSS} , C_{Pump} , C_{PV} , C_{Wind} , η_{P} , η_{KP1} , η_{KP2} , η_{Pumps} have been provided by the Greek DNO and are common values for the Greek IDNs.

The following assumptions have been considered: (1) The Proespera SHP is not available because the Reservoir 1 (Pezi) in Fig. 1, only release water between October and April, when there is an excess of water in the Pezi dam [9]. Thus, the Proespera and Kato Proespera reservoirs are considered as a closed system connected to the 2.7MW WPP within the HPP with water only flowing between them, working as a HPSS. In future work, the Pezi dam will be added by completing the system and having a full view of Ikaria; (2) The efficiencies, powers and flow rates of the pumping station and the SHPs in Fig. 1, are considered as constant values without taking into account their variations because of the head level of the reservoirs. This will be also added in next stages of the algorithm; (3) Pumping is allowed from all available RES.

The optimization framework is developed considering constraints of several assets, their CO₂ emissions and their associated costs as well as constraints related to the IDN operation, e.g., power balance, stability, etc. The objective is to minimize the CO₂ emissions. The mathematical framework is formulated as follows:

A. Constraints of Assets

Renewable curtailment: The power from RES as PVPPs and WPPs is divided in Used (U) power and Curtailed (C):

$$P_{WPP, PVPP} = P_{WPP, PVPP}^U + P_{WPP, PVPP}^C \quad (2)$$

The curtailment decisions are decided by the optimizer as a result of the objective function which minimizes the emissions.

Balance Power:

$$P_{LD} + P_{pumps} = P_{thermal} + P_{HPSS} + P_{WPP}^U + P_{PVPP}^U \quad (3)$$

The power losses within the IDN have not been considered, but they will be included in future work. The limits of P_{pumps}^t are given in Table I.

Synchronous Must Run (SMR): For stability and inertia purposes there must be a minimum ratio of demand covered with synchronous power, as specified within the IDN [8], [12].

$$\sum_i^n (P_{thermal}^i \cdot State_{ON,OFF}) + P_{NKP1} \cdot State_{ON,OFF} + P_{NKP2} \cdot State_{ON,OFF} \geq P_{SMR} \quad (4)$$

where n is the total number of generators, $P_{thermal}^i$ is the power generated by each thermal unit (diesel or mazut), P_N is the power generated by each SHPT, and $S_{ON,OFF}^t$ is the state of the thermal unit (1: ON, 0: OFF) at each time step. P_{SMR} is defined in Table I as % of total demand.

Total Hydro Power:

$$P_{HPSS} = P_{KP1} + P_{KP2} + P_p - P_{pump} \quad (5)$$

Proespera reservoir State of Charge (SOC) changes from time step t to the next time step $t+1$ in the order of [0,100]%

$$SOC_P^{t+1} = SOC_P^t - \frac{\Delta t}{E_{P,KP}^{Cap}} \cdot \left[\sum_{i=1}^2 P_{KP_i}^t \cdot \eta_{KP_i} - \frac{P_{Pump}^t}{\eta_{Pump}} \right] \quad (6)$$

Kato Proespera reservoir SOC change:

$$SOC_{KP}^{t+1} = SOC_{KP}^t - (SOC_P^{t+1} - SOC_P^t) \quad (7)$$

Diary cycle: It is assumed that both water reservoirs begin their operation at 50% SoC, i.e., 55 MWh. The use of this energy will lead to results distortion. To avoid this, final SOC must be the same than the initial one.

$$SOC_P^{t,max} \geq SOC_P^{t=0} \quad (8)$$

$$SOC_{KP}^{t,max} \leq SOC_{KP}^{t=0} \quad (9)$$

By defining it as an inequation the optimizer has more freedom. The optimisation will tend to get results where final SOC is near the starting point. Otherwise, costs and emissions would have been dedicated to store non-used water.

B. Costs of Different Assets

Thermal Generation:

$$C_{thermal} = \sum_i^n c_{unit}^i \quad (10)$$

$$C_{unit} = (m_{fuel} + ON \cdot m_{ON}) \cdot (c_{fuel} + c_{CO2} \cdot CO2_{fuel}) + c_{O\&M} \quad (11)$$

where m_{ON} is the amount of fuel needed to start the unit [t], ON shows if the unit has started in this iteration (from idle to working), c_{fuel} is the cost of the fuel [€/t], c_{CO2} is the cost

of CO2 emissions [€/t_{CO2}] and $CO2_{fuel}$ is the CO2 emissions per mass of fuel used [t_{CO2}/t_{fuel}] and m_{fuel} [t]:

$$m_{fuel} = \eta(LF) \cdot P_{gen} \rightarrow LF \text{ (Load Factor)} = \frac{P_{gen}}{P_N} \quad (12)$$

where $\eta(LF)$ is the consumption of the unit to produce a certain amount of electric power or energy [t/MWh] dependent on the Loading Factor (LF), P_{gen} is the unit generated power [MW] and P_N is the unit rated power [MW].

Renewable Generation:

For the rest of the generators (wind, PV, and hydro) the total cost has been calculated from unitary cost showed in Table I and energy produced according to:

$$Cost_{WPP/PVPP/hydro} = c_{WPP/PVPP/hydro} \cdot P_{WPP/PVPP/hydro} \quad (13)$$

C. Emissions of Different Assets

Thermal:

$$Emissions_{unit} = (m_{fuel} + ON \cdot m_{ON}) \cdot CO2 \text{ Factor}_{fuel} \quad (14)$$

Renewable Generation: Analogous to what it has been done with costs, for the rest of the generators (wind, PV, and hydro) the total emissions have been calculated from emissions coefficients of Table I and energy produced according to:

$$Emissions_{WPP/PVPP/hydro} = CO2_{WPP/PVPP/hydro} \cdot P_{WPP/PVPP/hydro} \quad (15)$$

D. Optimizer definition

In this framework, the Ikaria daily load and generation of [19] have been used. The optimization objective is the minimisation of system emissions, as it has been set as the major goal for SINNOGENES.

Emissions Minimization:

$$Emissions_{system} = E_{thermal} + E_{HPSS} + E_{WPP} + E_{PVPP} \quad (16)$$

Cost calculation is analogue to the emissions, according to:

Cost:

$$Cost_{system} = Cost_{thermal} + Cost_{HPSS} + Cost_{WPP} + Cost_{PVPP} \quad (17)$$

If the costs were considered in the objective function instead of the emissions, similar results may arise, since thermal units are the most expensive and polluting ones. For this reason, only the emissions have been considered in the objective function, but in the results, also the costs are calculated. All of these results were obtained thanks to the NEOS Server [20], [21], [22], and using the Knitro solver which is a nonlinear optimizer actually developed by Artelys, [23]. The interconnection between Samos and Ikaria IDNs is not modeled at moment in the optimization framework. In further studies it will be analyzed how this interconnection and Ikaria assets (RES, HPSS, etc.) can be utilized to satisfy the demand of Samos island, [24], in an optimized manner. In addition, based on the proposed framework, an ID optimization for voltage regulation and congestion management will be developed in future work considering detailed the detailed topology of the IDN and by performing quasi-steady-state power flow analysis to check the voltages at each node and possible contingencies. In this framework all assets of the Ikaria IDN, i.e., WPPs converter, PV converters and VSPs converters,

TABLE II
DEFINITION OF THE SCENARIOS

Scenario	Wind	Sun	Demand
1	Low	Low	Low
2	Low	Low	High
3	High	High	Low
4	High	High	High

Fig. 2. Profiles for: (a) the demand Consumed/Load; (b) the PV generation; (c) the wind generation, where (WG): Profiles for the WPP of 0.9MW outside the HPP; (WH) profiles for the 2.7 MW WPP in the HPP.

will be exploited in terms of both active and reactive power considering 15-minute resolution Weather data from [25] to forecast the short-term RES production.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

In this Section the simulation results are presented and discussed in detail. Four types of scenarios have been considered to evaluate the performance of the developed optimizer, with these scenarios being primarily dependent on the wind and solar generation profiles, along with the electricity consumption on the island of Ikaria. For each scenario, two distinct types of profiles have been delineated, termed as “high” and “low”. As suggested by their designations, the “high” profiles exhibit greater levels of generation and consumption, whereas the “low” profiles are characterized by reduced levels. Distinguishing generation (wind and sun) and consumption (demand), using these “high” and “low” profiles a total of 4 scenarios have been established. The combination of these variables for each scenario is presented in Table II, while the definitions of the individual profiles are illustrated in Fig. 2. These profiles were meticulously crafted utilizing historical data from Ikaria IDN, [19] to allow for the simulation of extreme scenarios. Note that in [19] only the data for the 0.9MW WPP outside the HPP is provided, thus, for the definition of the power profile for the 2.7MW WPP within the HPP, the data of the 0.9MW WPP are scaled up. The definition of scenarios is intended to test the capabilities of the DA tool in a variety of loading conditions.

From Fig. 3-(Left) it can be observed that the resulted values of Scenarios 1 and 2 respectively, with Low RES generation, are higher than those of Scenarios 3 and 4 with high RES generation, i.e., 0.33 tnCO_2/MWh and 0.64 tnCO_2/MWh . This is because in Scenarios 1 and 2 with low RES the IDN demand is mainly covered by the mazut generation. Regarding the tonnes of CO_2 emitted in Fig. 3-(Right), Scenario 2 is the one with highest value, 119.4 tnCO_2 , then Scenario 4 comes with 77.9 tnCO_2 and Scenario 1, with 44.2 tnCO_2 . Lastly, the

Fig. 3. For each Scenario: (Left) CO_2 emissions per MWh and total emissions; (Right) Cost per MWh generated and total cost.

Fig. 4. Generation profiles for each technology alongside the PVPP/WPP curtailment for (a) Scenario 1; (b) Scenario 2; (c) Scenario 3; (d) Scenario 4. The pump profiles illustrate the respective consumption.

Scenario with the lowest CO_2 generation is 3 with a value of 20.84 tnCO_2 . These findings demonstrate that the Scenarios with the highest load demand are the ones with the highest CO_2 emissions. Similarly, the cost production of energy works in the same way as the CO_2 emissions having more expensive values, 864 €/MWh and 948 €/MWh, in Scenarios 1 and 2. For Scenarios 3 and 4, the values are lower, 485 €/MWh and 703 €/MWh. The total costs of dispatch are ordered with the same distribution (Scenario 2, 4, 1, and 3) with 113,847 €, 85,489 €, 53,823 €, and 30,906 € respectively.

In Fig. 4, it is observed that the mazut generation depends directly on the IDN load and RES generation, with higher values of production in Scenario 2 (higher than 4.52MW). The lowest mazut production fits in Scenario 3, with a constant generation of 1.25 MW, which is a higher value than the difference between the demand and the low emissions generation (WPP, PVPP, SHPTs), due to the need to comply with SMR constraint. The SHPTs are used to cover peaks of demand without the need to increase the mazut generation. Actually, the hydro production rarely overpasses 1 MW. Meanwhile, the pumps are destined to prevent curtailment of the RES, with values that neither exceed 1 MW. This can be seen with the low values of curtailment that exist, e.g., in Scenario 4, there is only curtailment at 07:00, with a value of 0.042 MW which does not exceed the technical lower limit for pumping. Note that for figure higher resolution, the pumps consumption appears also with positive sign same as the generation. Finally,

a counter-intuitive behaviour has been observed in Scenario 4. Even if the objective is to minimize emissions, there is RES curtailment, e.g., at 07:00, with a value of 0.042 MW. This is because extra thermal generation will be needed to at least match pumping minimum of 0.125 MW, that will lead to higher emissions. Depending on parameters' value, it can be even observed that some hydro power will be needed to integrate all RES production.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

In this paper, an DA optimisation algorithm has been proposed for IDNs with HPSS and RES, like Ikaria, Greece. The results show that the cost and carbon footprint of generation mix is quite dependent on RES, as the backup generation consists on diesel and mazut units - mostly the mazut ones are used. With this straightforward approach, there is still undesirable RES curtailment, caused by minimum operation setpoint of pumping station. When curtailment is below minimum pump capacity, thermal generation would be needed. That will unexpectedly increase cost and emissions while integrating more RES to the system. With the definition of a dam closure constraint, i.e., the SoC at the end of the day should be the same as in the beginning, SHPTs' generation is only used to cover consumption peaks while mazut generation is established as the main generation due to its dispatchability and the SMR constraint. Regarding the emissions and cost, the results imply that, on the one hand lower RES generation cases result in higher values of emissions and cost per MWh due to the strong dependency on mazut generation, which is the most expensive technology. On the other hand, the scenarios with higher demand are the most of expensive and the ones with larger emissions, due to the need of more energy supply.

The DA optimization framework is applicable to any IDN as long as the respective parameters, e.g., costs, efficiency, etc., are adjusted. The proposed approach has been deployed within the Horizon Europe project SINNOGENES. In the near future, Ikaria IDN will be connected with the neighbour Samos IDN and then, with the mainland TS. Directions for future research include: (a) more detailed mathematical modelling of the HPSS components for all periods of the year; (b) a sensitivity analysis to quantify the impact of various parameters, e.g., efficiency of turbines and pumps, fuel prices, emission rates, on the IDN performance; (c) the study of the interconnection of Ikaria and Samos and with the mainland based on the DPs of the Greek DNO and TSO; (d) the ID Short-Term dispatch via active/reactive power dispatch for voltage regulation exploiting the reactive power from WPPs, PVs and the converters from VSPs or consider demand-response schemes. Finally, since the proposed framework will be a tool integrated to the SINNOGENES DT platform, future work will demonstrate the DT platform operation with all individual components.

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